

NextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Communication and dissemination plan
Deliverable number	D53 (Del. Rel. No. D10.2)
Revision	0
Status	Draft
Planned delivery date	28/02/2022
Actual date of issue	25/02/2022
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	BSC
Dissemination level	General public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

Work package in charge:

WP10, Storms & Society

Lead author:

Eulàlia Baulenas

Other contributing authors:

Dragana Bojović

Internal reviewer(s):

1st reviewer: Pajam Sobhani

2nd reviewer: Theresa Mieslinger

Contacts: eulalia.baulenas@bsc.es

Visit us on: www.nextgems-h2020.eu

Disclaimer: This material reflects only the authors view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

1 Executive summary	4
2 Conclusion & Results	4
3 Project objectives	4
4 The NextGEMS communication and dissemination plan	6
4.1 The principles permeating NextGEMS communication and dissemination activities	6
4.2 NextGEMS audience	6
4.3 Curating the message	7
4.4 Means and mediums	8
4.5 Summary of the communication and dissemination plan	9
4.6 Expected outcomes	11
4.7 Risk management	12
5 References (Bibliography)	13
6 Dissemination and uptake	14
6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience	14
6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience	14
7 Deliverable timeliness	14
8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	14
9 Sustainability	14
9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects	14
10 Full track of dissemination activities	14
11 Full track of publications and IP	14

1 Executive summary

This deliverable details the NextGEMS project communication and dissemination plan, which has as main objective the engagement of a broader audience reaching from the scientific community to many societal actor groups. This activity is part of WP10 and the storms & society theme, and the main two partners responsible for its implementation are BSC and LT. However, the plan will be deployed in close collaboration with all consortium members and project participants.

This deliverable is structured as follows: first, it details the importance of a good communication and dissemination strategy, and it defines the goals and scope of these activities. Secondly, it details our expertise and our audience, as well as the range of aspects that form its implementation. It concludes with exploring the channels which are used, as well as describing the risk and mitigation plan. There are three main innovations in distribution channels of the project results, additionally to the traditional approaches such as the official website, project deliverables and peer-reviewed articles. These innovations consist of the vlogs, scientific explainers and storylines. We detail them also in the section 4.3 and close this report with a section on the expected outcomes of this communication and dissemination plan.

2 Conclusion & Results

As the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy of any climate science-related project is crucial for the very success of it, the activities described in this deliverable are planned to start at the beginning of the project and to follow it until the end, and are based on the principles of visibility, transparency, plurality and usability. This is, achieving visibility of the project and its outcomes for a wide range of stakeholder circles; being transparent on the evolution of the NextGEMS scientific production; plurality in the perspectives included and reached with the different communication and dissemination products; and usability by bringing the scientific outputs to the right user by raising awareness on them. In this respect, the communication and dissemination plan has already started and has shown the first results with two videos that are shared on the website and through social media platforms such as Twitter and Vimeo, paving the way for project visibility and transparency. These videos have been a joint production of communication experts and the scientists that form part of the consortium members and target all the stakeholder groups that we aim to engage throughout the project. In this deliverable, further efforts are detailed in the curation of the message, means and mediums of this plan, as well as how these differ by the different stakeholder groups.

3 Project objectives

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
<hr/>	
O1	
<hr/>	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
<hr/>	
O2	
<hr/>	

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP10	Relevance in this deliverable?
Implement, monitor and adjust an effective strategy for NextGEMS co-production, communication & dissemination and video presence (O3)	yes
Connect model development and application communities and integrate potential users into the coproduction activities (coproduction process) (O3)	partially
Develop novel communication and dissemination forms to maximize the visibility and usability of the project and its results to target audiences (communication and dissemination) (O3)	yes
Provide technical and policy briefings to the competent authorities to make them aware of project results (policy dissemination) (O3)	yes

4 The NextGEMS communication and dissemination plan

This report details the communication and dissemination plan of NextGEMS. It starts with a brief discussion about the principles permeating our strategy, to detail next the activities that form the communication and dissemination plan.

4.1 The principles permeating NextGEMS communication and dissemination activities

A solid communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy has been called central to bridge the usability gap of climate science. The usability gap is the lack of incorporation of climate science and climate services in the decision-making processes of relevant societal actors, from policy-makers to private stakeholders and NGOs (Dilling & Lemos, 2011 [4]; Kirchhoff et al., 2013 [5]). Many scholars consider that the presence of this gap is partially due to the lack of attention to communication and dissemination activities. Proper communication has proven to turn the tables on actors adopting evidence-based adaptation, mitigation and disaster risk management policies (Terrado et al., 2018 [7]). This linkage between a good communication strategy and better climate responses is related to communication being key for any stakeholder engagement activities, and these activities are also central for climate science-related projects, including the success of the NextGEMS project (see deliverable 10.1 on knowledge co-production activities) (Bojovic et al., 2021 [1]).

Moreover, scholars working in climate science have pointed out towards the presence of domain and informational challenges. The domain challenge presents the scenario in which due to its innovative character, an emergent climate service market has unknown users, tasks and data. The informational challenge incorporates partially the usability gap: their novelty and complexity are barriers to its interpretation and use (Christel et al., 2018 [2]). For these reasons, the NextGEMS communication and dissemination plan puts the emphasis on having a strategy that will go parallel to the duration of the project, supporting all of efforts, including those tasks that do not encompass knowledge coproduction activities and thus are not user dominant. Because of this, the principles that guide the plan are those of visibility, transparency, plurality and usability (Norström et al., 2020 [6]). These principles are respectful of and are based on those outlined in the EU documents such as “Communicating your project”, including the H2020 Guidance Document “Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants” (2014) and the instructions on EU Guide to Science Communication¹. Plurality will be respected by adopting a gender- and diversity-aware approach when engaging with stakeholders, and when designing the several communication approaches which will be described next.

Among the best practices highlighted in the EU set of guidelines, NextGEMS is aligned with the allocation of enough resources to communication and dissemination activities, as key elements of WP10 and the storms & society theme. WP10 additionally includes all consortium members, whose collaboration in project communication and dissemination is guided by the project team of user engagement and communication experts. The guidelines further recommend the presence of a risk assessment and mitigation plan linked to the communication activities, as well as the setting of goals and objectives, the details of which we include in this report. Finally, we next share how we have identified our audience and divided them in near-field and far-field stakeholder groups that are the receivers each of different communication and dissemination strategies. And to conclude, we discuss how we curate our message for each of the medium and means used to build the communication strategy, distribute it and exploit it.

4.2 NextGEMS audience

In NextGEMS we divide the actors involved in the project between the profiles of near-field and far-field stakeholder groups, and we deploy different strategies accordingly of communication and dissemination, as it is explained in sections 4.3 and 4.4. Figure 1 below shows the communication and dissemination products that each of the stakeholder groups will receive.

The **near-field NextGEMS stakeholder groups** are formed by the following:

1. Scientists: earth science community and wider scientific community;
2. Users: users from renewable energy and fisheries;

¹EC (2014), “Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants”. H2020 Report.

Figure 1: NextGEMS stakeholder groups and means and mediums of communication.

3. Technologists: HPC technologists and high-capacity data experts;

The **far-field NextGEMS stakeholder groups** are formed by the following:

4. Policy-makers: policy and decision makers;
5. Broader user community: users from other sectors and domains, including climate services and met offices;
6. Public and media: general public, including local communities from West Africa, and journalists.

4.3 Curating the message

NextGEMS communication strategy builds on two ideas: tailoring communication and dissemination strategies by stakeholder group and putting the emphasis on what is communicated as well as the process of creating the message. These two ideas work together synergistically, allowing us to reach more effectively the audience and increase the awareness about the results of the project, but also a robust legacy with the uptake of its outputs by different communities. Specifically, NextGEMS communication and dissemination strategy focuses on how NextGEMS scientists establish facts, and reason from them with a particular emphasis on the role of knowledge gained from the project in this process. This is aligned with the “co-production turn” we embrace in NextGEMS (see D10.1), which, “reflects broader calls for science to become more responsive to societal needs (e.g., McNie 2007), as well as accountable to various publics and inclusive of other ways of knowing and being in the world (e.g., Leach et al. 2005).” (Daly & Dilling, 2019, p. 63 [3]).

For these several aims and reasons, we develop several types of messages packaged in three broad different type of formats: science explainers, storylines and policy briefs. These different product types can more effectively reach different audiences with the same curated message but in the most adequate format for them.

- **Science Explainers:** include material sourced from the NextGEMS scientists themselves. The scientists will use plain language to share the driving ideas and progress in the project, as well as how they reason about critical questions. An example could be on the topic of the role of deep convection in the tropics, the “Pattern Effect”, and its impact on allowable carbon emissions to meet a desired temperature target. Science Explainers will be developed in close collaboration with domain scientists and communication experts and emphasize not what to think but how scientists think. This approach gives access to information, and explanations, that are often not otherwise available to the public. The science explainers will be presented in different formats (e.g., text and audio), and will also provide the core elements for NextGEMS (progress) videos (see T10.4). The target audience for this type of message are mainly far-field NextGEMS stakeholder groups, but also near-field groups to update them efficiently on the progress of the project.

- *Storylines*: To provide a unity to different components of physical and social aspects of the researched phenomena, the project will use storylines. They will follow the scientific development and understanding of a few project elements, for instance, causes and effects of small changes in tropical sea-surface temperatures. Storylines will be used to emphasise developing understanding of how scientific outputs can be framed in the context of other socio-economic and environmental problems, as well as the impacts and implications of these chains of events. As part of the NextGEMS Vlog, Storylines will highlight what distinguishes SR-ESMs from previous generations of climate models, and may involve web-explorable story-maps, combining text, images and maps with geo-referenced data and simulation output. This type of material is especially adequate for near-field stakeholder groups, as it involves users additionally in its development process.

To inform policy makers and the European Commission, NextGEMS will additionally provide policy briefs. Two policy briefs will be delivered:

1. The first will focus on 'Building User Communities around Next Generation Earth System Models'. This will summarize our experiences in working to integrate User communities into the development of SR-ESMs. It will be intended to inform the European strategy for Earth-system modelling, particularly as a component of 'Destination Earth', and thus will target the European Commission and relevant Directorates-General.
2. The second will focus on 'Food Security in West Africa'. It will actively engage policymakers from the affected region (ACMAD, AGRHYMET, ECREEE, ECOWAS, African Climate Policy Center). It will present findings about the maritime productivity and their effects on fishery and the latest findings from investigating West African Monsoons and rainfall distribution and extremes in Sahel, a question that has been receiving increasing interest and triggering scientific and policy debates.

4.4 Means and mediums

The means and mediums of communication and dissemination activities refer to the channels with which we engage in a one-way or two-way exchange with the project stakeholders, both near and far-field groups. One-way communication means and mediums are those that provide information of a certain aspect to the community, whilst two-way exchange are more intense-driven forms of information exchange which allow additionally for conversations and other forms of multi-lateral interactions. Without being one superior to the other, both two forms fulfil different objectives. We next describe these different means and mediums, indicating to which form (one/two-way) they generally belong to.

Standard channels

For critical information dissemination, the NextGEMS communication strategy will continue to apply standard channels, such as social media, and visual identity elements, such as graphic charter, flyers, and roll ups. The website is the platform which will hold many of these products, and they will be additionally publicized through twitter as our main social media platform which allows for two-way exchanges. Additionally, partners' networks and its associated distribution channels will also engage in dissemination of the outputs produced under this plan. Finally, we will also use press releases for further dissemination of the results.

Internally, NextGEMS project partners benefit from communication through mailing list and the platforms such as Mattermost, which allows for opening several chats by selected topics, and gather.town, which is the platform used for the weekly office hours. Finally, we have a platform for sharing information about the simulations. This is the list of main communication forms, which except for the website they all allow for two-way communication forms:

- Website: www.nextgems-h2020.eu
- Twitter: [@nextgems_eu](https://twitter.com/nextgems_eu)
- **Internal communication tools**
 - Mailing list
 - Mattermost team
 - gather.town room
 - easy.gems documentation

The coordinator of these different tools is mainly WP1, but with the contributions of all partners.

Next generation Video Communication Concept

The project will produce four different types of videos, which we overall label as 'Vlogs', a powerful tool for science communication. The videos will make it possible for specialists to understand the project idea and to follow its progress, and at the same time reach out to broader audience such as policy and decision makers and the general public. Depending on the target audience NextGEMS Videos will be professionally produced or crowd sourced by the NextGEMS scientists. Some of the videos will be developed by Latest Thinking and consist of personal interviews with the project scientists providing plain language answers to a handful of simple questions, colourfully augmented by explanatory cartoons. The content of some of these videos are what we described in the previous section as 'Science explainers'. These NextGEMS Vlogs will provide coherent and plain language resources that can be used for media broadcasting of the project results, or for media briefs. Some of the communication materials will also be prepared in French, German or the native language of the NextGEMS scientists, to address a wider community of stakeholders.

To implement the Next generation Video Communication Concept, we use a web-based multi-media strategy with different types of video-based material:

- *NextGEMS Clips*: this is a short-format video, which in less than two minutes gives an overview of the project with the use of animations. The first example can already be found on the website and through this [link](#).
- *Research videos*: these videos will be departing from the outputs of NextGEMS research lines, specifically, the aim is to create an animated version of the published articles under the project. This is a communication strategy which has been increasing in recent years which aims at reaching a broader audience inside and outside the borders of the scientific community.
- *Results video*: this type of video shows the on-going research in layman terms, and it is meant to reach far-field stakeholders interested in the advancement of climate science. It integrates animations and the explanations given by NextGEMS scientists.
- *Progress videos*: finally, this last type of videos show the progress of the project. Especially, it shows the working process of NextGEMS. It can imply, for instance, the 'behind the scenes' of Hackathons (see [here](#)), or the other activities planned in the deployment of knowledge co-production activities.

In addition to the video concept of NextGEMS, a number of other (more classical) approaches will be used to enhance the communication and dissemination activities (see table in section 4.5).

Meetings, workshops and side events at conferences

Finally, among the means and mediums of communication, there are the meetings, workshops and side events organized at conferences. The planning of these activities will be conducted or supported by the storms & society theme, whose social scientists will help facilitation of these events. Particular attention will be given to engagement and selection of stakeholders invited to these meetings. These stakeholders will be contacted well in advance to save the date and informed about the objectives of the event. Prior to the event, the participants will receive information useful for a successful and efficient conduction of the meeting or workshop and be informed about the results -if signalling interest-, a posteriori.

4.5 Summary of the communication and dissemination plan

The below table shows the summary of the plan, linking target groups with the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

Target groups	Objectives	Dissemination & Exploitation Activities	Communication tools
Scientists: Earth science community and wider scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New knowledge coproduction with scientists from the Earth system community • Targeted knowledge dissemination to enhance uptake 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hackathons • Scientific journals • Open access repositories • Open Data • Conferences • Contribution to international scientific fora, e.g. IPCC and IPBES • Science dissemination platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project mailing list • partners' networks • Direct contacts • NextGEMS website and Vlog • NextGEMS research videos • NextGEMS progress videos • NextGEMS result video • Social media
Users from renewable energy and fishery (NUN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-exploration and definition of challenge problems • New knowledge coproduction & exploitation in hackathons • Demonstration of added value in pilot studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hackathons • Pilot studies development • Storylines • Science explainers • Meetings & Workshops • Side events at conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct communication • Communication through partners' networks • Project website and Vlog • NextGEMS research videos • NextGEMS progress videos • NextGEMS result videos
Technologists: HPC technologists and high-capacity data experts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness raising • Targeted knowledge exchange 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meetings • Science explainers • Technology scrums 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct communication • Communication through partners' networks • NextGEMS research videos • NextGEMS progress videos
Broader user community, including climate service and met offices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge exchange with the potential application community • Reaching out to potential users and enlarging the NUN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storylines • Science explainers • Meetings & workshops • Science dissemination platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication through mailing lists • Partners' networks • Project website and Vlog • NextGEMS clips • nextGEMS research videos • NextGEMS progress videos • NextGEMS results video • Social media
Policy and decision makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge dissemination for better informed policymaking • Demonstrating added value for decision making processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy briefs • Storylines • Policy events • Contribution to international scientific fora, e.g. IPCC and IPBES • Participation at high level political fora • Science dissemination portals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct communication • Communication through partners' networks • Project website and Vlog • NextGEMS research videos • NextGEMS results video

Target groups	Objectives	Dissemination & Exploitation Activities	Communication tools
Public and media: general public, including local communities from West Africa, and journalists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness raising • Involving scientific journalists • Involving media through multipliers at European and national level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storylines • Policy briefs • Workshops in West Africa • Science dissemination platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website and Vlog • Communication through partners' networks of journalists • Press releases • NextGEMS results video • Project visibility through science news services, such as EurekaAlert or idw online • Social media

4.6 Expected outcomes

The outputs expected from a robust communication and dissemination plan are described next.

Uptake of NextGEMS outputs in international fora

NextGEMS aims to robustly contribute to the, by now standard, assessment activities organised by the IPCC, and IPBES. In addition, NextGEMS will work with the German Excellence Cluster, Climate, Climate Change and Society (CLICCS) to support at least one of their yearly assessments, called Hamburg Climate Future Outlooks. These are syntheses focused on an overarching research question of possible and plausible climate futures. Working with CLICCS we will co-develop an edition of this Outlook around the scientific question of the Changing Climate of the Tropics.

Empowering involved researchers to become better communicators

The material for project communication and dissemination will be based directly or indirectly on the work of NextGEMS researchers. Especially, the base for the Vlog concept will feed on the key messages that we want to send to the public, as well as explanation of complex phenomena towards a non-academic audience. This process requires researchers to simplify aspects of their research and convey them in layman terms. With the support of communication experts, one of the expected outcomes is thus that scientist become better communicators of their outcomes, which will both benefit the dissemination and exploitation of NextGEMS results but also the scientists themselves who will hence obtain a new skill.

Good performance in key performance indicators (KPI)

Based on the H2020 guidance document on best practices for communication and dissemination plans, and to support the project KPI5 which measures dissemination and communication activities, we will monitor and report in the periodic Communication and Dissemination plans the following:

- Evidence of debates in the media
- Number of articles in the press
- Number of references in scientific publications
- Participation in project events and seminars
- Trends in website visits

Exploitation and sustainability beyond the lifetime of the project

The communication and dissemination concept, data management and exploitation strategy, including the contribution to The Hamburg Climate Future Outlooks Assessment Series, are all designed to sustain the impact of the project well after it concludes. In addition to standard knowledge and data management activities as outlined below, the two most important ways in which NextGEMS will ensure its legacy arises out of the basic design of NextGEMS itself. O1 has at its heart the idea of advancing and maintaining European leadership in the development of a new coordinated Earth-system modelling capability; and O3 endeavours to create a new Earth-system modelling culture, through the involvement of a much broader spectrum of expertise than is generally available within the present model-centred approach to model development. By meeting these objectives NextGEMS will influence the European culture of Earth-system modelling, as well as its roadmap for high-performance computing and data science.

4.7 Risk management

The table below describes the risks that we have identified for the implementation of the project, together with the assessment of their likelihood and suggestions for their mitigation.

Risk	Description	Level	Mitigation
Low project visibility and outreach of the Video Communication Concept	This risk could happen if the outputs produced under the communication and dissemination plan do not reach the intended audience	Medium probability – high impact	The simulations being performed in NextGEMS, are some of the most fascinating demonstrations of our science. Their visual appeal and the Vlog makes it very unlikely that the project won't capture the public imagination. Having science communication a professionals and the advisory board makes this risk very low. Additionally, we plan to share the video outputs across several platforms and conduct a social media campaign (on twitter) and the consortia members will be asked to share the videos in their networks.
Limited opportunities for conducting meetings or workshops	Risk of events being cancelled or postponed due to COVID-19	Low probability – medium impact	We will take advantage that both near and far-field stakeholder groups are acquainted with online meetings
Low engagement of near-field users	Low participation of the near-field stakeholder group due to insufficient engagement or saliency	Low probability – medium impact	Work more actively in reaching out to specific users and ask them and new users to "spread the word" (snowball effect). The storms & society group might add on with outreach activities in relevant events where the project could be showcased.
Low interest of researchers in supporting the Vlog	The scientists are ultimately producing the Vlog, with the support of WP10 team members. This risk can happen if other tasks get always prioritized in front of the Vlog.	Low probability – medium impact	The plan is to organise training for scientists on how to generate video content with minimal effort and high impact without prior camera expertise. Organizing these activities in a social way as part of Hackathons also makes it easier and more attractive for NextGEMS scientists to become involved.
Low impact on the stakeholder community	This risk can happen if the NextGEMS outputs are not well understood by the different stakeholder groups.	Medium probability – medium impact	NextGEMS is an ambitious project, and we expect take-up to be slow. However the long-term influence of the project is likely to compensate for difficulties stakeholders have in initially understanding its novelty. Persistence in dissemination and communication activities is an effective remedial action in these cases.

5 References (Bibliography)

- [1] Bojovic, D., st. Clair, A. L., Christel, I., Terrado, M., Stanzel, P., Gonzalez, P., & Palin, E. J. (2021). Engagement, involvement and empowerment: Three realms of a coproduction framework for climate services. *Global Environmental Change*, 68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102271>
- [2] Christel, I., Hemment, D., Bojovic, D., Cucchiatti, F., Calvo, L., Stefaner, M., & Buontempo, C. (2018). Introducing design in the development of effective climate services. *Climate Services*, 9, 111–121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CLISER.2017.06.002>
- [3] Daly, M., & Dilling, L. (2019). The politics of “usable” knowledge: examining the development of climate services in Tanzania. *Climatic Change*, 157(1), 61–80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-019-02510-w>
- [4] Dilling, L., & Lemos, M. C. (2011). Creating usable science: Opportunities and constraints for climate knowledge use and their implications for science policy. *Global Environmental Change*, 21(2), 680–689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GLOENVCHA.2010.11.006>
- [5] Kirchhoff, C. J., Lemos, M. C., & Dessai, S. (2013). Actionable knowledge for environmental decision making: Broadening the usability of climate science. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 38, 393–414. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-022112-112828>
- [6] Norström, A. v., Cvitanovic, C., Löf, M. F., West, S., Wyborn, C., Balvanera, P., Bednarek, A. T., Bennett, E. M., Biggs, R., de Bremond, A., Campbell, B. M., Canadell, J. G., Carpenter, S. R., Folke, C., Fulton, E. A., Gaffney, O., Gelcich, S., Jouffray, J. B., Leach, M., ... Österblom, H. (2020). Principles for knowledge co-production in sustainability research. *Nature Sustainability*, 3(3), 182–190. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0448-2>
- [7] Terrado, M., Christel, I., Bojovic, D., Soret, A., & Doblaz-Reyes, F. J. (2018). Climate Change Communication and User Engagement: A Tool to Anticipate Climate Change. In *Climate Change Management* (pp. 285–302). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-70479-1_18

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

There is a link to the deliverable 10.1 "Coproduction Plan", as well as to the deliverable D1.7 "Exploitation Plan".

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon, 19.10. - 22.10.2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - Activity: NextCalendArt 2022

11 Full track of publications and IP

No publications so far.